

A STUDY OF EFFECT OF INSTITUTIONAL CLIMATE ON MENTAL HEALTH OF B.Ed. TEACHER-TRAINEES

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Abstract- The purpose of this study is to find out the effect of institutional climate on mental health of B.Ed. teacher-trainees. Descriptive survey method was used for this study. Sample consisting 640 B.Ed. teacher-trainees was selected by using stratified random sampling technique from 11 B.Ed. colleges of Bareilly district. Institutional Climate Scale (ICS) developed by researcher and Mental Health Inventory (MHI) developed by C.D. Aagshe and R.D.Helode (2008) used for data collection. Data analysis using Mean, S.D., one way and two-way ANOVA. Finding reveals that there was significant effect of institutional climate on mental health of B.Ed. teacher-trainees and no significant interaction effect was found between institutional climate and gender on mental health of B.Ed. teacher-trainees.

Keywords: Institutional Climate, Mental Health, B.Ed. Teacher-Trainees.

Introduction:

The climate of teacher education institution nurtures the quality of education. Quality oriented teachers are reshaped and reoriented in these teacher education institutes which help them to rebuild the nation. The climate of teacher education institution refers to the administration, infrastructure, qualified teachers, management and resources etc. which help them in development of knowledge, understanding, ability to analyse, synthesize and evaluate skills (physical and mental) as well as develop desirable values and attitude among institution students. Positive institutional climate promotes development of academic achievement, personality, mental health and social behaviour etc. Research done by **Adjeiet al. (2017)** indicates that institutional climate of teaches education promotes academic achievements of students. Thus we can say that good relationship between institutional climate and individual's personal variable (mental health, personality attitude, academic achievement etc.). Library, laboratories, Wi-Fi internet, computer system, overhead projector and other information communication technology (ICT) are also included in institutional climate.

Mental health is an important determinant of one's integrated personality and balanced behaviour, identified on the basis of the level of his/her adjustment to own self, others and environment (**Kaur et al.,2015**). According to Wikipedia mental health is a state of emotional and psychological wellbeing in which an individual is able to use his/her cognitive and emotional capabilities and meet the ordinary demand of everyday life.A mentally healthy individual can adjust properly with environment, family and contribute for the society's progress and betterment (**Lewkan,1993**). Mental health is the adjustment of human being with the world and also with one another to the maximum of effectiveness and happiness. It is the ability to maintain socially considerate behaviour, a happy disposition, an even temper and alert intelligence (**Meninger,2004**).

Institutional climate plays an important role in student's life. In this specific context the present research will undertaken to specifically provide empirical answers of these questions like what is the effect of institutional climate on mental health, what is the interaction effect of institutional climate and gender on mental health of B.Ed. teacher trainees. Up to date numbers of study have reported the ways in which institutional climate and mental health of students. A study was conducted on mental health of middle school students in relation to school climate by **Franco et al. (2022)**. Findings of this study revealed that there found a significant positive relationship of mental health with institutional climate. Similarly, **Jessiman et al. (2022)** reported significant relationship between school culture and mental health of secondary school students of UK. **Aldridge & Mc Chesney (2018)** found significant positive relationship between school climate and mental health. A positive school climate is linked to a wide range of outcomes, including the growth of children and adolescents. In another study, **Kohoulat et al. (2015)** found positive relationship between school climate and mental health. Similarly, **Suldo et al. (2012)** found adolescents' mental health were more strongly correlated with school climate. Review of related literature reveals that various studies had been conducted school/institution climate and mental health, but it was found that no study has been conducted effect

of family climate on mental health of B.Ed. teacher trainees. Hence, the researcher has decided to undertake, the study of effect of institutional climate on mental health of B.Ed. teacher trainees.

Objectives of the Study:

1. To study the effect of institutional climate on mental health of B.Ed. teacher-trainees.
2. To explore the difference on mental health of male and female B.Ed. teacher-trainees.
3. To find the interaction effect between institutional climate and gender on mental health of B.Ed. teacher-trainees.

Hypotheses of the study

1. There is no significant effect of institutional climate on mental health of B.Ed. teacher-trainees.
2. There is no significant difference on mental health of male and female B.Ed. teacher-trainees.
3. There is no interaction effect between institutional climate and gender on mental health of B.Ed. teacher-trainees.

Research Design & Methodology:

The researcher used Descriptive survey method. Population of the present study consists of all the teacher-trainees of B.Ed. colleges affiliated to M.J.P. Rohilkhand University, Bareilly. Sample of 640 teacher-trainees of 11 B.Ed. colleges of Bareilly district selected with the help of stratified random sampling techniques. Institutional Climate Scale (ICS) developed by researcher and Mental Health Inventory (MHI) developed by C.D. Aagshe and R.D.Helode (2008) were used for the study. Data analysis using Mean, S.D., one way and two-way ANOVA.

Data analysis and interpretation:

Hypothesis 1: There is no significant effect of institutional climate on mental health of B.Ed. teacher-trainees.

Table 1.1: Descriptive statistics of mental health of B.Ed. teacher-trainees

Institutional Climate Group	N	Mean	S.D.
Good Institutional Climate	81	23.22	4.522
Moderate Institutional Climate	489	21.85	4.054
Poor Institutional Climate	70	20.51	4.272
Total	640	21.88	4.185

One way ANOVA has been performed for testing the hypothesis-1. The result of ANOVA for mental health have been shown in table-1.2

Table 1.2 Summary of ANOVA (Effect of institutional climate on mental-health of B.Ed. teacher-trainees.)

Source of Variance	df	SS	MSS	F-Value
Between Groups	2	276.961	138.481	8.081*
Within Groups	637	10916.287	17.137	
Total	639	11193.248		

(*significance level 0.05)

Table 1.2 shows that the main influence of institutional climate on B.Ed. students' mental health has a computed F-value of 8.081 ($p < 0.05$), which is significant at 0.05 significance level for df (2,637). The significant F-value reveals that institutional climate affect the mental health of B.Ed. teacher trainees. Thus, the null hypothesis (H.2) – “There is no significant effect of institutional climate on mental health of B.Ed. teacher trainees” is not accepted.

As ‘F-Value’ for main effect of institutional climate on mental health has found significant, In order to determine the significant effect of the various institutional climate groups on the mental health of B.Ed. students, Scheffe's Post Hoc Test has been used. The results of numerous comparisons are shown in Table 1.3.

Table-1.3: Post Hoc Test (Scheffe) [Multiple comparison of good, moderate and poor institutional climate groups on mental health]

Institutional Climate Group (I)	Institutional Climate Group (J)	Mean Difference (I-J)
Good Institutional Climate	Moderate Institutional Climate	1.374*
Good Institutional Climate	Poor Institutional Climate	2.708*
Moderate Institutional Climate	Poor Institutional Climate	1.334*

(*The mean difference is significant at the 0.05 level)

From Table 1.3, it can be seen that B.Ed. teacher trainees having good institutional climate are significantly different from the B.Ed. students having moderate institutional climate on mental health with the mean difference (1.374, $p < 0.05$). When the mental health of B.Ed. students in the good institutional climate group and the poor institutional climate groups is compared, mean difference found to be (2.708, $p < 0.05$), which is significant at the 0.05 significance level. A significant mean difference (1.334, $p < 0.05$) is observed among the B.Ed. students having moderate institutional climate and the B.Ed. students having poor institutional climate on their mental health.

The above analysis indicated that all three groups of institutional climate are significantly different from each other. The main reason behind this may be that democratic, favourable and healthy institutional climate motivates the B.Ed. students to improve their skills and achieve their goals. They performed better in their academic performance and feel happy and satisfied, so they reported high level of mental health. Unfavourable institutional climate do not provide proper guidance, cooperation and healthy learning environment to their students, so their students showed lower level of mental health.

Hypothesis2: There is no significant difference on mental health of male and female B.Ed. teacher-trainees.

Table 2.1: Descriptive statistics of mental health of male and female B.Ed. teacher-trainees.

Institutional Groups	Climate	Gender	Mean	S.D.	N
Good Institutional Climate		Male	23.87	4.508	39
		Female	22.62	4.504	42
		Total	23.22	4.522	81
Moderate Institutional Climate		Male	21.96	4.174	235
		Female	21.75	3.945	254

	Total	21.85	4.054	489
Poor Institutional Climate	Male	20.12	4.341	31
	Female	21.41	4.050	39
	Total	20.76	4.272	70
Overall	Male	21.98	4.354	305
	Female	21.82	4.031	335
	Total	21.90	4.185	640

Two-way ANOVA has been performed for testing the hypothesis-2. The result of two-way ANOVA for mental health have been shown in table-2.2

Table 2.2 Summary of ANOVA (Effect of different dimensions family climate on mental-health of male and female B.Ed. teacher-trainees.

Source of Variance	df	SS	MSS	F-Value
Institutional Climate Group	2	302.724	151.362	8.879*
Gender	1	2.724	2.724	0.160
Institutional Climate Group × Gender	2	106.189	53.095	2.890
Error	634	10808.503	17.048	
Total	639			

(*significance level 0.05)

Findings of institutional climate on mental health have been already discussed. Table 2.2 shows that the F-value for the gender influence on mental health is 0.160 ($p > 0.05$), which is not statistically significant at the 0.05 level for df (1,634). Therefore, there are no significant differences in the mental health of B.Ed. students who are male and female. Thus, the null hypothesis (H.2) – “There is no significant difference on mental health of male and female B.Ed. teacher trainees” is accepted.

H.3. There is no significant interaction effect between institutional climate and gender on mental health of B.Ed. teacher trainees.

The estimated "F-Value" for the interaction effect of institutional climate and gender on mental health is found to be 2.890 ($p > 0.05$), which is non-significant at 0.05 significance level for df (2,634). This information is shown in Table 2.2. This demonstrated that the joint effects of institutional climate on the mental health of B.Ed. students is unaffected by gender. Thus, the null hypothesis (H.3)-“There is no significant interaction effect between institutional climate and gender on mental of B.Ed. teacher trainees” is accepted.

Fig.1: Interaction Effect between Institutional Climate and Gender on Mental Health

It reveals that male and female B.Ed. teacher trainees of all three groups of institutional climate showed non-significant mean difference on mental health. From figure-1, it is observed that the mean score of male B.Ed. teacher trainees having good institutional climate ($M=23.87$) on mental health have a small difference with the mean scores of female B.Ed. teacher trainees having good institutional climate ($M=22.62$), but this mean difference is not significant. Male B.Ed. teacher trainees of having moderate institutional climate reported fewer mean scores ($M=21.96$) on mental health than the female B.Ed. teacher trainees having moderate institutional climate ($M=21.75$), but it is not significant. A non-significant mean difference was found between the male B.Ed. teacher trainees having poor institutional climate ($M=20.12$) and the female B.Ed. teacher trainees having poor institutional climate ($M=21.41$) on mental health. Overall the mean score of male B.Ed. teacher trainees (21.98) on mental health have a small difference with the mean score of female B.Ed. teacher trainees (21.82), but this mean difference is not significant. The reason may be that males and females of all three groups of institutional climate have given democratic and similar opportunities in family, school, institution and society.

Conclusions:

Main effect of institutional climate on mental health is found to be significant ($F=8.879$, $p<0.05$), effect of gender on mental health is observed to be non-significant ($F=0.160$, $p>0.05$), whereas a non-significant joint effect of institutional climate and gender is found on mental health of B.Ed. teacher trainees. Thus, it may be said that the main effect of institutional climate on mental health is independent of the effect of gender.

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